

分段模型连续性的直接概率测量和推断

A Direct Probability Measure and Inference for Continuity of Piecewise Models

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【术语变更】 本文将随机变量改名为可变属性 (Variable Attribute), 英文术语简化为 Vattribute。

【Terminology Change】 In this paper, Random Variable is renamed to Variable Attribute, and then Variable Attribute is simplified to Vattribute.

提要 假定两分段模型在自变属性上的临界点被以一种加权期望所估计, 则两个相邻临界模型在该期望临界点处的预测值之间一定会存在着一个随机的抽样连接变异, 而这个变异通常不会恰好等于 0, 可以成为估计临界模型在该临界点处是否连续的基础。以二维空间的两段直线模型为例, 该连接变异的测量将是一个简单的平面几何面积, 而该面积占整个样本最大可测空间面积的比例可以作为一个关于两段模型连续性的直接概率测量。由于该概率是经验性的且存在抽样误差, 它需要接受一个是否为零的差异性检验和概率推断。

关键词 分段回归、二维两分回归、加权期望临界点、分段模型的连接变异、直接概率测量、连续性检验

ABSTRACT Assuming that a threshold over the independent vattribute of a dichotomic model is estimated using a weighted expectation, there must be a random sampling connection variation between the predicted values of two adjacent piecewise models at this expected threshold. This variation is usually not exactly equal to zero, and can serve as the basis for estimating whether the piecewise models are continuous at the threshold. Taking a two-segment rectilinear model in two-dimensional space as an example, the measurement of such a connection variation is a simple planar geometric area, and the ratio of this area to the maximum measurable area of the entire sample space can be used as a direct probability measure of the continuity of the two-segment model. Because this probability is empirical and subject to sampling error, it requires a difference test to determine whether it is zero and a probability inference.

KEYWORDS Piecewise regression, two-dimensional dichotmic regression, weighted expected threshold, connection variation of piecewise models, direct probability measure, continuity test

1. 问题的提出 (The Rising of Problems)

任何统计方法最初可能不过是一个简单思想, 最终发展到可以恰当的数学形式表达, 以便实现数据分析和认知。作为一种方法或策略, 分段回归分析需要在一个可被分割的连续可测样本空间里找到一个或多个临界点, 以便将整个样本空间分割为两个或多个临界子空间, 并分别为每个子空间拟合一个临界回归模型, 从而以一组可变模型来描述和预测整个空间上的复杂关系。

Any statistical method may start out as a simple idea and eventually develop into an appropriate mathematical form for data analysis and cognition. As a method or strategy, piecewise regression analysis needs to find one or

more thresholds in a continuous and measurable sample space that can be segmented, so as to segment the entire sample space into two or more thresholding subspaces, fit a threshold regression model respectively over each subspace, and thus to describe and predict complex relationships over the entire space with a set of variable models.

1.1 现行算法的基本程序 (The basic procedure of the current algorithm)

在分段回归占据主流的算法是在 1959~1979 年间建立起来的，其流程可简单归纳如下：

- 1) 基于数据迭代拟合分段回归模型
- 2) 基于最小合并残差平方和确定最优分段模型
- 3) 基于强制连续性假定解联立方程组得到最优临界点
- 4) 用彼替法为最优临界点构建可信区间
- 5) 检验两个相邻最优分段模型间的差异性
- 6) 平滑化两个相邻最优模型的连接

由此可知，这其中不再讨论分段模型的连续性，因为它已强制性地假定了两段模型在临界点处的连接变异总是等于 0。

When reading the literature on piecewise regression, the author found that for any possible methodological researchers in this field, although different people used different terms at different times and in different application areas to develop and express their own methodologies, all the problems, in fact, they encountered and tried to solve were basically the same. Therefore, although countless predecessors have made great contributions in this field, only a very few pioneers have laid the main path for the methodological development in this field. Here, the author is willing to briefly summarize the algorithms and processes that have occupied the mainstream in this field for a long time as follows:

- 1) Fit piecewise regression models based on data iteration
- 2) Determine the optimal piecewise model based on minimum combined residual sum of squares
- 3) Solve a system of simultaneous equations based on the forced continuity assumption to obtain the optimal threshold
- 4) Construct a confidence interval for an optimal threshold with bootstrapping method
- 5) Test the difference between two adjacent optimal piecewise models
- 6) Smooth the connection of two adjacent optimal models

From this, we can see that the continuity of piecewise models is no longer discussed here, because it has enforcedly assumed that the connection variation of the two piecewise models at the threshold is always equal to 0.

1.2 数值型最优化的错误根源 (Source of mistake of numerical optimizations)

作者先后在 2007 和 2009 的两次 JSM 报告上对上述方法提出了批判，并于 2025 年在其著作《哲学之于统计学》的第九章完善了其会议文章中关于分段回归的理论和法学阐述，并最终在该书中完善了关于连续性测量和检验的算法。

The author criticized the above method in two JSM (Joint Statistical Meetings) presentations in 2007 and 2009, respectively, and improved the theoretical and methodological explanation of piecewise regression in his conference articles in Chapter 9 of his book *Philosophy of Statistics*, and finally improved the algorithm for continuity measurement and testing in the book.

作者通过定义随机对应这个概念指出了众多统计方法中普遍存在的过拟合的理论和算法上的根源，由此彻底否定了数值型最优化在统计算法构建中的应用性地位，因为一切基于样本数据构建的优化算子本质上都是可变属性。由于任何可变属性的最大值和最小值是其边界测量，它们在样本的可测范围内具有最大的不稳定性和不可靠性，因而，用所谓的“优化算子”的某个极值做统计决策也必然是最不稳定和最不可靠的。而且，优化算子是基于样本数据的算法，其最大值或最小值有可能是一个离群值，这将加大统计决策的危险性。可以确信，很多统计方法中存在的过拟合就是唯一地由此类最优化导致的。若从概率论中“连续空间上的点测度的概率为 0”的定理来看，优化算子的某个极值对应于目标可变属性的统计期望的概率也为零或趋于零。

By defining the concept of random correspondence, the author pointed out the theoretical and algorithmic roots of overfitting that is prevalent in many statistical methods, thereby completely denying the applicability of numerical optimization in the construction of statistical algorithms, because all optimizers constructed based on sample data are essentially attributes. Because the maximum and minimum of any attribute are its boundary measurements, they are extremely unstable and unreliable within the measurable range of a sample. Therefore,

using extreme values of a so-called “optimizer” to make a statistical decision is inevitably the most unstable and unreliable. Furthermore, since an optimizer is an algorithm based on sample data, its maximum or minimum may be an outlier, which increases the risk of the statistical decision. It is believed that the overfitting found in many statistical methods is uniquely caused by this type of optimization. According to the theorem in probability theory that “the probability of a point measure over a continuous space is 0”, the probability that a certain extremum of an optimizer corresponds to the statistical expectation of the target vattribute is also zero or tends to zero.

从抽样分布的角度看，对一个优化算子的计算不仅输出了其自身的一个完整抽样分布，而且该分布还关联着一个目标可变属性的完整抽样分布。令人不可思议的是，信奉数值型最优化的人们却在优化算子的完整分布中选择了其最大或最小值所对应的目标可变属性的一个随机点测量作为了他们所期望的统计决策。然而，这两者之间并不存在可期望的对应。因此，我们可以说，数值型最优化在统计学中没有合法性。它是一个原本不该发生的根本性错误，而其得以发生的原因则应该是确定性数学中的“函数极值思维”在随机系统中的滥用。这是统计方法论发展史上一个长期的历史性悲剧。

From the perspective of sampling distribution, the computation of an optimizer not only outputs a complete sampling distribution of its own, but also associates with a complete sampling distribution of the target vattribute. Surprisingly, believers in numerical optimization choose a random point measure of the target vattribute corresponding to the maximum or minimum in the optimizer’s complete distribution as their expected statistical decision. However, there is no expected correspondence between the two. Therefore, we can say that numerical optimization has no legitimacy in statistics. It is a fundamental mistake that should never have occurred, and its occurrence is likely due to the misuse of the “functional extremum thinking” in deterministic mathematics in andom systems. This is a long-standing historical tragedy in the development of statistical methodology.

1.3 优化算子改为权重算子使用 (Optimizer used as a weighter)

从一个抽样分布来看，如果总体中确实存在一个临界点和临界回归关系，那么，在样本数据构成的分布空间内，每个样本点都以自身所在的位置对临界点发生在哪里都有一份可变的贡献或权重。我们所要做的就是将这份贡献测出来。事实上，构建一个优化算子的目的正是为了了解其数值上的随机变异对目标可变属性的影响，而且对优化算子的计算过程不仅可以得到其完整的分布，还可以得到目标可变属性的完整分布。令人遗憾的是，所谓的最优化决策选择了这个分布的极值来对应目标可变属性的统计期望。因此，作者认为摆脱数值型最优化以及由此引发的过拟合的恰当方式是将优化算子改为权重使用，由此可计算目标可变属性的加权期望，而基于加权期望的统计决策一定是唯一可期望的决策。

From the perspective of a sampling distribution, if there truly exists a threshold and a threshold regression relationship in the population, then within the distribution space formed by the sample data, each sample point has a variable contribution or weight based on its location to the occurrence of the threshold. What we need to do is to quantify this contribution. In fact, the very purpose of constructing an optimizer is to understand how its numerical randomness affects the target vattribute, and the computation of the optimizer can yield its complete distribution. Unfortunately, the so-called optimization-based decision selects the extreme value within this distribution to correspond to the statistical expectation of the target vattribute. Therefore, the author believes that the appropriate way to overcome numerical optimization and the consequent overfitting is to transform the optimizer into a weighter. In this way, we can compute the weighted expectation of the target vattribute, and any statistical decision based on a weighted expectation must be the only rationally expected decision.

在最优化算法中人们通常使用 $\arg \min$ 或 $\arg \max$ 构建算法表达式。这里，作者建议用 $\arg \exp$ 替代前两者，因为它们在统计学中将不再有方法论上的意义。正式地，如果 W 是权重算子（表示样本点的贡献）， X 是目标可变属性（即某个可随机变异的 measurable 属性），则 $\arg \exp$ 将输出一个关于 X 的加权期望，记为：

In optimization algorithms, people usually use $\arg \min$ or $\arg \max$ to construct algorithm expressions. Here, the author suggests replacing these with $\arg \exp$, since $\arg \min$ and $\arg \max$ no longer hold methodological significance in statistics. Formally, if W is the weighter (i.e., a weighting operator, representing contributions of sample points), and X is the target vattribute (i.e., a measurable attribute that can vary randomly), $\arg \exp$ outputs a weighted expectation with respect to X , written as:

$$\bar{x}_w = \arg \exp_x E[M(W, X)] \quad (1)$$

其中 $M(W, X)$ 是关于权重 W 和目标随机可变属性 X 所构成的二维可测联合空间的一个随机测度分布，期望算子 \mathbb{E} 取自该联合随机性。 $\arg \exp_x$ 表示期望估计的算法，其下标 x 表示加权期望针对的是 X 而非 W 。where $M(W, X)$ is a random measure distribution over the two-dimensional measurable joint space of formed by the weight W and the target randomly variable attribute X , and the expectation operator \mathbb{E} is taken with respect to

this joint randomness. The notation $\arg \exp_x$ indicates that it is an expectation algorithm, and the subscript x indicates that the weighted expectation is taken with respect to X , not W .

1.4 临界点的加权期望和分段模型的连接变异 (Weighted expectation of threshold and connection variation of piecewise models)

在改变了优化算子的用途后，问题变成了如何优化权重算子的定义和构建，也即这个权重算子如何充分使用一切有价值的样本信息，并且样本信息的使用还必须避免冗余。换句话说，权重的构建应做到“无信息损失和无信息冗余”。作者认为这是权重构建中应遵循的两个原则。只有这样，对临界点的加权期望估计才有可能无偏。作者在《哲学之于统计学》的第九章详细列出了分段回归的迭代搜索过程中可以输出的全部可用信息，经过一番深思熟虑，作者用这些信息构建了多达数十种的权重算子，并通过一个随机模拟试验对其逐一进行验证，从中发现了一个在现有概念和理论体现下无可挑剔的定义作为唯一的权重定义。

After changing the usage of an optimizer, the question becomes how to optimize the definition and construction of a weighter, that is, how can this weighter fully utilize all valuable sample information while avoiding redundancy? In other words, the weighter should be constructed with “no information loss and no information redundancy.” The author believes that these are two principles that should be followed in weight construction. Only in this way can the weighted expectation estimate of a threshold be unbiased. In Chapter 9 of *Philosophy of Statistics*, the author lists in detail all the available information that can be output during the iterative search process of piecewise regression. After a careful consideration, the author used this information to construct dozens of weighters and verified them one by one through a random simulation experiment. From this, he found an impeccable definition under the existing concepts and theories as the only weighter definition.

给定二维联合可测空间上的一个随机样本 $[X\{x_i\}, Y\{y_i\}] (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ 。首先拟合模型 $y = a + bx$ ，且以 X 为被分割属性。如果按 X 迭代时构建的权重 W_x 满足无偏性，根据式(1)， X 上一个临界点的加权期望估计（用 \bar{x}_Δ 表示）可表达为：

Given a random sample $[X\{x_i\}, Y\{y_i\}] (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ over a two-dimensional jointly measurable space, first we fit the model $y = a + bx$ with X as the segmented variable. If the construction of weight W_x satisfies the unbiasedness, according to formula (1), the weighted expectation estimate of a threshold, denoted by \bar{x}_Δ , on X can be expressed as:

$$\bar{x}_\Delta = \arg \exp_x E[M(W_x, X)] \quad (2)$$

其中 X 是被分割的可变属性。 $\arg \exp_x$ 与 E 连用表示针对该二维空间的 X 输出计其加权期望 \bar{x}_Δ 。据此可将原始样本分为两段，并拟合两段模型：

Where X is the attribute being segmented. $\arg \exp_x$ used together with E , represents the weighted expectation \bar{x}_Δ of the output of X in this two-dimensional space. Based on this, the original sample can be divided into two segments and fitted with a two-segment model:

$$\begin{cases} {}^1\hat{Y} = a_1 + b_1X & \text{if } X \leq \bar{x}_\Delta \\ {}^2\hat{Y} = a_2 + b_2X & \text{if } X \geq \bar{x}_\Delta \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

显然，两段模型在该期望临界点处预测值的绝对差不会恰好等于零，也即，此时两段模型之间的连接变异（用 CV_y 表示）发生在因变属性 Y 上：

Obviously, the absolute difference of the predicted values of the two-segment models at this expected threshold will not be exactly equal to zero, that is, the connection variation (represented by CV_y) between the two piecewise models occurs on the dependent attribute Y :

$$CV_y = | {}^1\hat{Y}_\Delta - {}^2\hat{Y}_\Delta | = |(a_1 + b_1\bar{x}_\Delta) - (a_2 + b_2\bar{x}_\Delta)| \quad (4)$$

同理，拟合模型 $x = c + dy$ 。以 Y 为被分割属性，且按 Y 迭代时构建的权重 W_y 也应满足无偏性，则 Y 上一个临界点的加权期望估计可表达为：

Similarly, we can fit model $x = c + dy$. With Y as the segmented variable, and the weight W_y constructed when iterating according to Y should also satisfy the unbiasedness, the weighted expected estimate of the threshold on Y can be expressed as:

$$\bar{y}_\Delta = \arg \exp_y E[M(W_y, Y)] \quad (5)$$

相应的分段模型可表达如下：

The corresponding piecewise model can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} {}^1\hat{X} = c_1 + d_1Y & \text{if } Y \leq \bar{y}_\Delta \\ {}^2\hat{X} = c_2 + d_2Y & \text{if } Y \geq \bar{y}_\Delta \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

此时两段模型在该期望临界点处的连接变异（用 CV_x 表示）将发生在因变属性 X 上：

and the connection variation (represented by CV_x) of the two piecewise models at the expected threshold will occur on the dependent variable X :

$$CV_x = |{}^1\hat{X}_\Delta - {}^2\hat{X}_\Delta| = |(c_1 + d_1\bar{y}_\Delta) - (c_2 + d_2\bar{y}_\Delta)| \quad (7)$$

上述分析过程和结果可形成一个如下的简单图示，其中 CV_y 和 CV_x 在由该样本构成的空间上会形成一个封闭的平面矩形，该矩形的面积 $S_{CV} = CV_y \times CV_x$ 占全样本最大可测空间的面积的比可以作为两个分段模型之间在该期望临界点处是否连续的直接概率测量。

The above analysis process and conclusion can form a simple diagram as follows, in which CV_y and CV_x form a closed planar rectangle in the space formed by the sample. The ratio of the area of this rectangle ($S_{CV} = CV_y \times CV_x$) to the area of the maximum measurable space of the entire sample can be used as a direct probability measurement of whether the two segmented models are continuous at the expected critical point.

Figure 1. A visual illustration of the connection variation in piecewise regression

然而，当设置一个被分割属性时，原本在该被分割属性上的连接变异被转移到了另一个属性上，因此，该面积之比会存在夸大，因此，作者建议将这个直接概率测量调整为：

However, when a segmented variable is set, the connection variation originally on the segmented variable is transferred to another variable. Therefore, the area ratio will be exaggerated. Therefore, the author recommends adjusting this direct probability measurement to:

$$S_{cv} = \frac{1}{2} \times CV_y \times CV_x \quad (8)$$

其中分母 2 是一个校正因子，可被理解为该模型仅涉及两个可变属性之间的关系，且连接变异仅在两者之间相互迁移。

The denominator 2 is a correction factor, which can be understood as that the model only involves the relationship between two vattributes, and the connection variation only migrates between the two.

1.5 分段模型的离断性和连续性 (Discontinuity and continuity of piecewise models)

这里首先需要指出的是, 统计学中的离断性和连续性概念与确定性数学中的同一概念不同。在数学中, 一个模型要么是连续的, 要么是不连续的。以图 1 为例, 在数学意义上, 其中的分段模型是离断的或不连续的。然而, 从统计学的角度来看, 分段模型的两个线段在临界点处可能看起来不连续, 即使它们事实上可能是连续的; 反之, 它们可能看起来连续, 但实际上却可能是不连续的。两段模型在临界点处的连接变异通常包含着随机误差和系统变异, 因此, 应以概率方式评估这些段是连续还是不连续。如果随机误差大到不可忽略, 则非零连接点变异主要可归因于抽样变异, 并且分段模型连续的概率充分高。相反, 如果随机误差可以忽略不计, 则连接变异主要反映真正的结构性差异, 并且临界点处不连续的概率充分高。

It should first be pointed out here that the concepts of discontinuity and continuity in statistics differ from their deterministic mathematical counterparts. In mathematics, a model is either discontinuous or continuous. Taking **Figure 1** as an example, in a mathematical sense, the piecewise models are disconnected or discontinuous. However, in a statistical sense, two linear segments of a piecewise model may appear discontinuous at the threshold, even though they may actually be continuous, and conversely, they may appear continuous while being truly discontinuous. The connection variation of two segments at the threshold contains both random error and systematic error. Whether the segments are judged to be discontinuous or continuous should therefore be assessed probabilistically. If the random error is large enough to be non-negligible, the nonzero connection variation may be attributed primarily to sampling variability, and the probability that the piecewise model is continuous is sufficiently high. Conversely, if the random error is negligible, the connection variation mainly reflects genuine structural differences, and the probability of discontinuity at the threshold is sufficiently high.

样本的最大可测空间理论上应该是总体的一个参数, 由于抽样的有限性, 我们只能通过样本提供的信息来定义这个空间的大小。从图 1 可以看出, 这个空间的大小正是分段模型及其期望临界点可能发生变异的空间, 其几何大小 (用 S_{xy} 表示) 按下式计算:

The maximum measurable space of a sample should theoretically be a parameter of the population. Due to the limitation of sampling, we can only define the size of this space through the information provided by the sample. As shown in Figure 1, the size of this space is precisely the space in which the segmented model and its expected threshold may vary. Its geometric size (denoted by S_{xy}) is calculated as follows:

$$S_{xy} = [\max(X) - \min(X)] \times [\max(Y) - \min(Y)] \quad (9)$$

虽然一个给定的样本在该空间上具有一定的表现形态, 我们不能因此认定总体中的模型表现就是如此。由于抽样的随机性, 样本在这个最大可测空间内的回归模型在形态上是不确定的。尽管如此, 这并不妨碍我们痛过一次抽样对总体的情形形成某种认知。因此, 对于一个给定的样本, 其分段模型的连续性测量应该以其最大可测空间为参照。于是可为两个模型在期望临界点处的离断性 (用 D_{pm} 表示) 定义如下测量:

Although a given sample exhibits a certain morphology within this space, we cannot therefore assume that the model in the population will behave in the same way. Due to the randomness of sampling, the regression model of the sample within this maximum measurable space is morphologically uncertain. Nevertheless, this does not prevent us from forming a certain understanding of the population through a single sampling. Therefore, for a given sample, the continuity measurement of its piecewise models should be based on its maximum measurable space. Thus, the following measure can be defined for the discontinuity (denoted by D_{pm}) between two models at the expected threshold:

$$\text{离断性(Discontinuity):} \quad D_{pm} = \frac{S_{cv}}{S_{xy}} \quad (10)$$

于是, 连续性 (用 C_{pm} 表示) 测量可被定义为:

The continuity (denoted by C_{pm}) measure can then be defined as:

$$\text{连续性(Continuity):} \quad C_{pm} = 1 - D_{pm} \quad (11)$$

由此可见, 离断性和连续性是关于分段模型在临界点处的同一表现的一对互斥且互补的测量。显然, D_{pm} 和 C_{pm} 的可测空间都是 (0,1), 且 C_{pm} 越大, 分段模型的连续性就越高; 反之, 分段模型的离断性越高。

It follows that discontinuity and continuity are a pair of mutually exclusive yet complementary measures of the same manifestation of piecewise models at their threshold. Obviously, the measurable space of both D_{pm} and

C_{pm} is (0, 1), and the larger the C_{PM} , the higher the continuity of piecewise models will be; otherwise the higher the discontinuity of piecewise models will be.

1.6 离断性和连续性的标准误(Standard error of discontinuity or continuity)

任何样本统计量都存在抽样误差，而抽样误差可被分为两大类，即系统误差和随机误差。尽管我们可以将抽样误差分为这两大类，但却无法它们的大小区分开来。因此，不得不为一个统计量构造一个所谓的标准误的统计量，以便为进一步区分两类误差奠定基础。

Any sample statistic is subject to sampling errors, which can be divided into two types: systematic error and random error. Although we can categorize sampling errors into these two types, we cannot distinguish their magnitudes. Therefore, we have to construct a so-called standard error for each statistic to lay the foundation for further distinguishing the two types of error.

这里的离断性 D_{pm} 和连续性 C_{pm} 也都是样本统计量，必然存在两类抽样误差。由于离断性和连续性是一对互斥互补的测量，两者的标准误是同一的，可按下式定义：

The discontinuity (D_{pm}) and continuity (C_{pm}) here are also sample statistics, and therefore necessarily subject to two types of sampling error. Because discontinuity and continuity are a pair of mutually exclusive and complementary measurements, their standard errors are identical and can be defined as follows:

$$SE_d = SE_c = \sqrt{\frac{D_{PM} \times (1 - D_{PM})}{n - 2}} = \sqrt{\frac{D_{PM} \times C_{PM}}{n - 2}} \quad (12)$$

其中 n 是样本量。

in which n is sample size.

1.7 离断性或连续性的检验 (Test for discontinuity or continuity)

分段模型在临界点处的连接变异是一个随机现象，由此得到的离断性或连续性测量上也是一个**随机现象**。正如检验样本均数与总体均数为 0 的差的逻辑，或者，检验样本相关系数是否为 0 的逻辑，我们需要检验连接变异是否为 0，也即离断性是否为零。如果离断性以充分大的概率为 0，则分段模型将以充分大的概率连续；反之，若离断性不为 0，则分段模型就不是连续的。为此，可为离断性检验定义一个 t 统计量如下：

The connection variation of piecewise models at threshold is a random phenomenon, and the discontinuity or continuity measurement based on this is also a random phenomenon. Just like the logic of testing the difference between a sample mean and the population mean of 0, or the logic of testing whether a sample correlation coefficient is zero, we need to test whether the connection variation is 0, that is, whether the discontinuity is zero. If the discontinuity is 0 with a sufficiently large probability, then the piecewise models will be continuous with a sufficiently large probability; conversely, if the discontinuity is not 0, then the piecewise models are not continuous. To this end, a t -statistic may be defined for discontinuity test as follows:

$$t_d = \frac{D_{PM} - 0}{SE_d} = \frac{D_{PM}}{SE_d} = \sqrt{\frac{(n - 2) \times D_{PM}}{C_{PM}}} \quad (13)$$

同理，连续性检验的 t 统计量可被定义为：

Similarly, the t -statistic for the continuity test can be defined as:

$$t_c = \frac{C_{PM} - 0}{SE_d} = \frac{C_{PM}}{SE_d} = \sqrt{\frac{(n - 2) \times C_{PM}}{D_{PM}}} \quad (14)$$

由于离断性和连续性是对同一样本的一对互斥且互补的测量，以上两个检验对于同一样本是等价的。两个检验的自由度均为：

Since discontinuity and continuity are a pair of mutually exclusive and complementary measurements of the same sample, the above two tests are equivalent for the same sample:

$$v = n - 2 \quad (15)$$

2. 应用实例 (An Example of Application)

2.1 实例模型的连接变异 (The connection variation of the example models)

以下图片展示了一个两段直线模型的应用实例。其中横轴上的临界点的加权期望为 40.36，相应的两段模型为：

The following image shows an example of a two-segment straight line model. The weighted expectation of the critical point on the horizontal axis is 40.36, and the corresponding two-segment model is:

$$\begin{cases} {}^1\hat{Y} = -1.7365 + 0.0876X & \text{if } X \leq 40.36 \\ {}^2\hat{Y} = 0.0453 + 0.0435X & \text{if } X \geq 40.36 \end{cases}$$

由此计算得到 Y 的预测值之差为：

$$CV_y = |-1.7365 + 0.0876 \times 40.36 - 0.0453 - 0.0435 \times 40.36| = 0.001924$$

纵轴上的临界点的加权期望为 2.219。相应的两段模型为：

$$\begin{cases} {}^1\hat{X} = 22.844 + 10.405Y & \text{if } Y \leq 2.219 \\ {}^2\hat{X} = 2.718 + 20.116Y & \text{if } Y \geq 2.219 \end{cases}$$

由此计算得到 Y 的预测值之差为：

$$CV_x = |22.844 + 10.405 \times 2.219 - 2.718 - 20.116 \times 2.219| = 1.4227$$

图9.1.12 基于凸权均数的全域模型和分段模型以及加权临界点
Figure 9.1.12 Cmean-based fullwise model and piecewise models with weighted threshold

由此得到该样本分段模型在两个坐标轴上的联合连接变异为：

$$S_{cv} = \frac{1}{2} \times CV_y \times CV_x = \frac{1}{2} \times 0.001924 \times 1.4227 = 0.00136864$$

2.2 离断性/连续性的测量 (Discontinuity/Continuity measure)

该样本在横轴 X 和纵轴 Y 上的最大可测空间分别为：

The maximal measurable space of the sample on the horizontal axis X and vertical axis Y are:

$$R_X = 49.3; \quad R_Y = 3.01$$

于是，本例分段模型的离断性和连续性测量分别为：

Thus, the discontinuity and continuity measures for the example of piecewise models are:

$$\text{离断性(Discontinuity): } D_{pm} = \frac{S_{cv}}{S_{xy}} = \frac{0.00136864}{49.3 \times 3.01} = 0.0000092$$

$$\text{连续性(Continuity): } C_{pm} = 1 - D_{pm} = 1 - 0.0000092 = 0.9999908$$

2.3 离断性/连续性的检验 (Test for discontinuity/continuity)

已知本例的样本量 $n = 35$, 因此, 离断性和连续性测量的标准误的计算如下:

Given that the sample size in this example is $n = 35$, therefore, the standard errors of the disconnection and continuity measures are calculated as follows:

$$SE_d = SE_c = \sqrt{\frac{0.0000092 \times 0.9999908}{35 - 2}} = 0.000528$$

2.3.1 对离断性的 t 检验 (Test for discontinuity)

检验的假设如下:

H_0 : 该样本的总体离断性为 0, 即 $D_{pm} = 0$, 分段模型在临界点处是连续的;

H_1 : 该样本的总体离断性不为 0, 即 $D_{pm} \neq 0$, 分段模型在临界点处是离断的。

检验的概率水准为: $\alpha = 0.01$

检验统计量 t_d 的计算如下:

The hypotheses tested are as follows:

H_0 : The population discontinuity of the sample is zero, that is, $D_{pm} = 0$, and the piecewise models are continuous at the threshold;

H_1 : The population discontinuity of the sample is not zero, that is, $D_{pm} \neq 0$, and the piecewise models are discontinuous at the threshold;

The probability level of the test is: $\alpha = 0.01$

The test statistic t_d is calculated as follows:

$$t_d = \frac{0.0000092 - 0}{0.000528} = 0.0174$$

本例的自由度 $\nu = 35 - 2 = 33$ 。由 t 统计量到 p 值的转换得到 $p_{0.0174, 33} = 0.9862 \gg 0.01$, 由此推断本例分段模型的离断性测量中随机误差大到不可忽视, 在概率 0.01 的水平上接受 H_0 , 拒绝 H_1 , 分段模型在临界点处是连续的。由于离断性是一个直接概率测量, 该样本在临界点处发生离断的概率约为 0.0000092, 趋于 0。

In this case, the degrees of freedom $\nu = 35 - 2 = 33$. Converting the t -statistic to a p -value yields $p_{0.0174, 33} = 0.9862 \gg 0.01$. This indicates that the random error in the discontinuity measurement of the piecewise models is significant and cannot be ignored. At a probability of 0.01, we accept H_0 and reject H_1 , indicating that the piecewise models are continuous at the threshold. Since the discontinuity is a direct probability measure, the discontinuity probability of this sample at the threshold is approximately 0.0000092 that tends to 0.

2.3.2 对连续性的 t 检验 (Test for continuity)

检验的假设如下:

H_0 : 该样本的总体连续性为 0, 即 $C_{pm} = 0$, 分段模型在临界点处是离断的;

H_1 : 该样本的总体离断性不为 0, 即 $C_{pm} \neq 0$, 分段模型在临界点处是连续的。

检验的概率水准为: $\alpha = 0.01$

检验统计量 t_c 的计算如下:

The hypotheses tested are as follows:

H_0 : The population continuity of the sample is zero, that is, $C_{pm} = 0$, and the piecewise models are discontinuous at the threshold;

H_1 : The population continuity of the sample is not zero, that is, $C_{pm} \neq 0$, and the piecewise models is continuous at the threshold.

The probability level of the test is: $\alpha = 0.01$
The test statistic t_c is calculated as follows:

$$t_c = \frac{0.9999908 - 0}{0.000528} = 1893.922$$

本例的自由度 $\nu = 35 - 2 = 33$ 。由 t 统计量到 p 值的转换得到 $p_{1893.922, 33} < 0.00001 \ll 0.01$ ，由此推断本例分段模型的连续性测量中随机误差小到可忽略，在概率 0.01 的水平上拒绝 H_0 ，接受 H_1 ，分段模型在临界点处是连续的。由于连续性是一个直接概率测量，该样本在临界点处连续的概率约为 0.9999908，趋于 1。

In this case, the degrees of freedom $\nu = 35 - 2 = 33$. Converting the t -statistic to a p -value yields $p_{1893.922, 33} < 0.00001 \ll 0.01$. This indicates that the random error in the continuity measure of the piecewise models is negligible. At a probability of 0.01, we reject H_0 and accept H_1 , indicating that the piecewise models are continuous at the threshold. Since continuity is a direct probability measure, the continuity probability that this sample is continuous at the threshold is approximately 0.9999908 that tends to 1.

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(Note: The main ideas of this paper was presented at the *Section of Advances in Statistical Inference* sponsored by IMS, 2025 Joint Statistical Meetings in Nashville, TN, USA)